

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

MODERNIZATION OF HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATION AT THE CURRENT STAGE OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Objective. The article highlights the ways to modernize higher medical education at the current stage of social development, points out the possibilities of improving the management of educational and educational processes thanks to the partnership of the I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University and the Erasmus+ Program of the European Union "Innovative Rehabilitation Education – Introduction of new master degree programs in Ukraine 2018-2021".

Keywords: Rehabilitation Education, Erasmus+ Program.

In accordance with the latest trends in the development of modern society, such features as dynamism and variability are becoming increasingly characteristic of education systems.

The objective conditionality of the reconstruction of the higher school is determined by the change in the social order, which is currently formed by market relations.

In accordance with the requirements of the Constitution of Ukraine, the Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education", education is characterized as a process of learning and upbringing in the interests of the individual, society, and the state and which is aimed at the development of individuality, talents, mental abilities and physical perfection of the individual.

The development of higher education in the conditions of the unfavorable influence of the current economic and social factors, the possibility of transition from the uniformity of functioning to diversity and development are based on traditional strengths, such as integrity, stability and flexibility, which allow to successfully overcome negative external influences and reveal internal, unused reserves

Sometimes the conservatism of traditionalism makes it difficult to implement the principles of democracy and the development of student self-government in the work of a higher school.

The traditional system of the educational process is in contradiction with the laws and regularities of physiological activity and management theory.

The lecture-practical system of higher educational institutions is now in most cases characterized by the reproducibility of the material of the educational classes perceived by the students. The micro-normativity of the educational material is related to conducting classes of the classical type on their systematization. The classical lecture is currently the leading type of educational activities that violate the logic of educational activities, which is especially not desirable in senior courses.

Individualization of education and differentiation of learning activities create a situation of choice for the teacher and student of the form of classes and provide the opportunity for further self-education and professional education.

The transformation of purposefulness, diagnosis of pedagogical analysis, democratization of the organization of control, regulation and correction within the framework of the modern concept of higher school management are related to the prospect of implementing scientifically based new pedagogical technologies and systems for organizing the educational process.

The leading factor in the transition of the higher school to a new qualitative stage is the implementation of advanced pedagogical theories by the forces of advanced teams of professorial and pedagogical staff of the departments.

Determining the perspectives of higher education development management is a complex systemic task. The principle of modularity provides for the integrity and completeness of the completeness and logic of the construction of units of educational material in the form of modules, within which the educational material is structured in the form of educational elements. A training course on the subject is constructed from the modules. Elements inside the module are interchangeable and movable. The assimilation of educational material takes place in the process of the completed cycle of educational activities. The flexibility of such a solution is based on the variability of the levels of complexity and difficulty of educational activities.

Since modular training involves the goal of forming a complete self-education in a student, this entire process is built on the basis of a conscious purposefulness with a hierarchy of close (knowledge, abilities, skills), medium (general scientific skills and abilities) and perspective (development of personal abilities) goals. Awareness of educational activity transfers the teacher from the mode of informing to the mode of

counseling, but within the framework of subject-subjective relations in the system: "teacher-student", and the student is rebuilt from his reproductive educational activity (where memory is mainly involved) on the mode of development of cognitive interest and development of cognitive activity and activity.

Modular programs and modules are built on the target basis of information material with the coordination of complex and integration and private goals, the completeness of the educational material, the relative independence of the elements in the module, with the implementation of feedback, with the optimal transfer of information and methodical support.

The criteria of the content of the modules include the diagnosis of the goal, the adequacy of the educational material to the goal, the organization of cognitive activity and the prospects of using its results, the hierarchical structure of the experience, the significance of the controlled characteristics, and the openness of the diagnosis.

Positive changes in the organization and informative provision of independent work led to the strengthening of the practical application of knowledge in the training of specialists.

Repeatedly repetitive educational activity of the student during independent work at an adequate individualized level of complexity of the educational material translates skills into skills. At all stages, the teacher should act as the organizer of the process, and the student performs the role of independent, consistent research of the problem, the solution of which leads to a previously defined structure of knowledge, abilities and skills.

The teacher's functions can vary from individually controlling to consulting and coordinating. The dynamics of such technology lies in the variability of the content and the possibilities of transitioning learning to both the type of activity and the methods of action. The flexibility of this technology is explained by adaptation to the individual characteristics of students due to the diagnosis of knowledge, rates of assimilation and individualization of learning. Acquaintance of students (in the first lesson) with the entire program and complex didactic goal, taking into account close, medium and distant tasks, ensure the perspective of the technology. Its parity is performed on the basis of the relatively independent nature of the student's educational work and the joint choice of the optimal learning path by the teacher and the student.

The process of education and upbringing is a way of functioning of the pedagogical system, the content of which is the management of human development. The activity of the teacher's and student's position consists in the fact that each of them, to one degree or another, acts as a subject of management of his activity and behavior and the behavior of others. This approach to the educational process significantly increases the effectiveness of educational activities.

According to the general guidelines, the modernization of the higher school involves the reorientation of educational activity from a purely lecture-informational to an individually differentiated personal form. That is, the ideology of a modern higher school is to

change the technology of "killing knowledge" to the technology of "organization of self-education" of students. So, the current state of information provision of the lecture is reduced to a conceptual and overview definition of the problem and the analysis of possible directions for its solution.

Moving away from the stereotypes of reproductive education and focusing on independent mastery of knowledge is the order of the times.

A higher school should equip students with deep and comprehensive knowledge, involve students in scientific and educational work, and develop scientific research skills. These tasks are carried out using various forms, methods, techniques in higher education. Among them, a high-quality lecture plays one of the leading roles. In the lecture, the presentation of the material should be combined with interactive teaching techniques and educational research. It should awaken students' thoughts, make them reflect on the subject of study, look for answers to the questions that arise, stimulate students to search for unknown, interesting and important scientific provisions.

In order to activate students' cognitive activity, it is advisable to use (in addition to classical) such types of lectures, which are quite relevant in the period of the credit-module system of education, as they give the teacher more opportunities to exercise control through students' creative thinking, reflections and judgments.

The reorientation of professors and teaching staff and students to individual and differential personal forms of education was also reflected in the conduct of laboratory, practical and seminar classes. The use of interactive forms during their implementation gives students the opportunity to independently master practical knowledge, and posing and solving problems activates students to scientific searches for their solutions.

The introduction of the latest learning technologies, along with the expansion of the potential of students' independent work, allows to increase the availability of educational services, create an effective system of continuous education, and also reduce the weekly classroom load of students.

Possibilities are expanding and the use of didactic material of the new generation is improving: electronic textbooks, virtual teaching aids.

The introduction of modern forms of organization of the educational process and the implementation of forms of conducting practical work: conducting classes in small student groups, case studies, conducting situational seminars and business games, training specialists in conditions closest to practical activities in the future specialty provide much greater efficiency in training highly qualified specialists than traditional teaching. This way of learning makes it possible to ensure and preserve its characteristic features in the studied content. The renewal of the system of organization of the educational process is connected with its structural and functional restructuring in the process of assimilation of new educational technology, strengthening the role of motivation and stimulation of scientific and pedagogical personnel within the framework of a person-oriented approach to management activities in order to achieve the final results planned by its subjects.

The effectiveness of the whole system of organizing the educational process is interrelated with the organizational structure and technology of the pedagogical process.

Therefore, nowadays in higher educational institutions, pedagogical technologies should be aimed at person-oriented pedagogical technologies of learning.

As part of the partnership between the Ternopil National Medical University and the Erasmus+ Program of the European Union "Innovative Rehabilitation Education - Introduction of new master degree programs in Ukraine 2018-2021", two Physical Therapy

Laboratories have been created on the basis of the Department of Medical Rehabilitation.

With the funds of the European Union, a wide list of equipment for practical training of students of the specialty "Physical therapy" was obtained. Ergotherapy", in particular: MOTomed viva 2 rehabilitation device, universal stairs for learning to walk with an inclined S/U ramp, rehabilitation tables with electric height adjustment, manual table for rehabilitation with load, PARAMOBIL orthopedic device with static-dynamic module, universal cabin for suspension therapy WSC-4.

In laboratory No. 2, students have the opportunity to study and work with the most modern equipment, namely: the TYMO stable platform for functional assessment and rehabilitation of balance disorders and the

PABLO rehabilitation complex for computer correction of gross and fine motility disorders of the muscles of the upper limb. The purchased equipment is effectively used in the educational process of students and

for the rehabilitation of patients with disorders of the nervous system and musculoskeletal system.

Thus, thanks to the university's participation in the Erasmus+ program, an important step has been taken, bringing the quality of training of physical therapists at TNMU as close as possible to European standards.

TYMO stable platform.

Balance is assessed in 4 positions: M1 - position standing on a hard surface with eyes open, M2 - position standing on a hard surface with eyes closed, M3 - position standing on a soft surface with eyes open, M4 - position standing on a soft surfaces with closed eyes.

Evaluated indicators: distance traveled - distance of body movement to maintain balance in centimeters; medio-lateral deviation – movement in the frontal plane in centimeters; anterior-posterior deviation – movement in the sagittal plane in centimeters; the area of the statokinesiogram is the area in which the center of pressure moves while maintaining balance (cm²); average movement speed – the average value of body movement speed during the balance test (cm/s); feedback system - visual, vestibular, somatosensory components in percentages, Romberg index (IR) values provide information on the dependence of the movement strategy on the visual channel of receiving information. The Romberg index demonstrates the relationship between the visual analyzer, lateral deviation and vertical elevation of the foot. The reflex-controlled index assesses the presence of reflex sequences of movements. The CNS-driven index assesses the presence of CNS-generated movement sequences that are controlled by the brain.

In addition to research, it is possible to treat balance and coordination disorders thanks to the patient's performance on the platform of tasks visualized in the form of a computer game.

Complex for the correction of disorders of gross and fine motility of the muscles of the upper limbs Pablo

It allows you to evaluate the functional capabilities of the upper limb at the beginning and during the treatment process, as well as to carry out training using interactive programs.

The target group for using the Pablo system consists of neurological, orthopedic and pediatric patients with deficits in upper extremity movement control, force application and control, precision, coordination and balance.

Pablo connects to a PC using wireless sensors, which allows you to use it without restrictions.

Assessment tools:

Isometric strength measures such as cylindrical grip, planar grip, pincer grip, and interdigital grip can be assessed and trained. In addition, the location of the hand in space (in relation to other parts of the body) is evaluated, which allows you to train a wide variety of movements in the entire upper limb. It allows to measure the amplitude of movements of all joints of the upper limb and to carry out its correction.

Game programs: goal-oriented tasks, accompanied by a sound and visual signal, as well as tactile feedback, provide support for maximum concentration of attention and motivation. Movement on the screen is controlled by the strength and amplitude of the movement of the sensor. 10 difficulty levels provide training within the patient's motor skills and sense of touch.

One device allows you to assess the strength of both flexors and extensors, the device is designed to work in the finger - hand - hand range.

Thus, the partnership between the Ternopil National Medical University and the Erasmus+ Program of the European Union "Innovative Rehabilitation Education - Introduction of new master degree programs in Ukraine 2018-2021" made it possible to improve students' assimilation of practical skills and to improve higher medical education at the I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University.

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